

Animal Stool Collection CRF

#	Question	Variable
1	Today's date	DD/MM/YYYY
2	Household ID	
3	Visit	Baseline Visit Follow-up Visit 1 Follow-up Visit 2 Follow-up Visit 3
4	Sample ID	
5	Sample Type	Stool from floor Direct sample from animal (poultry)
6	Place found?	Inside house Outside house
7	Animal Species?	Cattle (beef) Cattle (dairy) Goat Sheep Pigs Chickens Equines Dogs Doves Guinea fowl Turkeys Ducks Cats Gecko Rat Other (specify) Unknown
<i>You have completed data collection for this animal.</i>		
<i>Please complete a stool sample collection form for 4 household animals in total</i>		
8	Staff signature	
9	Time and Date	MM:HH DD/MM/YYYY